

Systematic Literature Review on Negotiation & Conflict Management

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Abstract:

In this article, we investigated the existing knowledge of Negotiation aiming at mapping the evolution of the main theories up to 123 years through systematic literature review. N = 4,894 publication records were extracted from Google Scholar and Scopus through keyword searching, resulting in more than seven million citations. Based on these records, the study performed bibliometric analysis. A careful content analysis revealed that the scholarly research revolves mostly around five themes: (i) Negotiation; (ii) International Negotiation, (iii) Business Negotiation, (iv) Bargaining, and (v) Conflict Management. Furthermore, the number of citations on Negotiation more than tripled in the last two decades and might double in the coming decades. This study also suggests recommendations for future studies.

Keywords: negotiation, content analysis, citation analysis, literature review, network text analysis.

Introduction

In this work we addressed Negotiation and Conflict Management, two subjects that have attracted scholars' attention over the past decades (Dias, 2020; Raiffa, 1982; Fisher et al., 1981; Sebenius, 1992; Ury, 2015; Susskind & Field, 1996; Salacuse, 2008; Pruitt & Rubin, 1986; Thomas & Killman, 1974, 2002; Blake & Mouton, 1964; Liebrand & McClintock, 1988; McClintock & Allison, 1989; Van Lange et al., 1997; Murphy, Ackermann & Handgraaf, 2011; Olekalns, & Adair, 2013b; Dias et al., 2023). Thus, we conducted a systematic literature

review on the subjects from 1900 to 2023, resulting 4,893 publications, according to Table 1:

Table 1. Articles Investigated (1900-2023)

Timeline	Total
1900-1949	19
1950-1969	78
1970-1979	139
1980-1989	413

1990-1999	1.207
2000-2009	1.765
2010-2023	1.273
Total	4.894

Negotiation is defined as a process of communication by which “two or more persons seek to advance their interests through joint action.” (Salacuse, 2006). Also, "Negotiation is a process of communicating back and forth to reach a joint decision." (Fisher et al., 1981).

Conflict Management is in turn defined as a practice to identify incompatibilities and disagreements, dealing with them effectively (Thomas & Kilmann, 1974).

Despite the topic relevance, there are still some relevant aspects to be clarified, addressed into four research questions: RQ1: How did Negotiation and Conflict Management evolve throughout the last 120 years? RQ2: What is the most prominent and cited topic of both? RQ3: What are the leading authors in the fields? RQ4: What is the geographical spread of citations?

In this research, we drove our attention to the evolution of Negotiation and Conflict Management as described in the upcoming sections.

Methodology

In this study, we employed a qualitative, multi-method approach, including a literature review on Negotiation, content, citation, and text network analysis, to reach our conclusions. This study utilized a systematic literature review (SLR) methodology to ensure an exhaustive and transparent coverage of the literature (Denyer & Traffield, 2009). It was chosen due to its widespread adoption in bibliometric analyses (Prashar et al., 2020; Singh & Walia, 2020). The subsequent subsections elaborate on the methodology in detail.

Review Objectives

We followed Goyal & Kumar's (2020) lead in establishing the review's primary objective: map the global scientific literature on Negotiation and Conflict Management. In addition, we followed Zahoor & Talba's (2020) organization of research objectives into sub-objectives, which included (i) mapping the Leading Publications on the subject; and (ii) identifying influential research studies based on Citation network and text network analysis to provide emergent trends on the subject. The overall valid sources and exclusions are illustrated in Table 2:

Table 2. Total Sources

Feature	Negotiation	Business Negotiation	International Negotiation	Bargaining	Conflict Mgmt	Total
Scopus+						
Google Scholar	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Exclusions	27	27	25	16	11	106
Valid sources	973	973	975	984	989	4.894

Table 2 shows close numbers of valid sources per theme (variation in nine percent max in the number of sources), thus keeping the number of sources consulted as constant as possible within methodological limitations.

Research Strategy

The systematic literature review covered 5,000 publications, unfolding nearly seven million citations. We also employed the software Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007) to investigate the

research coverage from 1900 to date. The search parameters included only words in the English Language. Then, the academic dataset selected was the Google Scholar and Scopus databases. After the first round with Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007), a text network analysis was performed to identify the most relevant emerging themes; they were used as keyword entries in a new iterative round. Then, the data were content, citation, and text network analyzed. The emerging themes were also

analyzed geographically, through Google My Maps® (see Figure 4).

Screening and Selection

Firstly, we investigated the keywords “Negotiation” and “Conflict Management,” setting the software above to include

publications and exclude patents as a search default. Thus, the total search involved 5,000 articles, with 106 exclusions due to duplications, totaling 4,894 articles investigated (see Table 2), resulting into 7,023,074 citations, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Number of Citations per Theme

Negotiation				Conflict Mgmt	Total
Negotiation	Business Negotiation	International Negotiation	Bargaining		
1.805.746	2.764.672	1.948.974	244.266	259.416	7.023.074

Figure 1. Research Design

Data Analysis

Five themes were revealed, and an iterative process led to several sessions to accomplish the research findings. The themes were organized into groups, and subgroups, divided according to relevance, such as Group 1: Negotiation;

Group 2: International Negotiation; Group 3: Business Negotiation; Group 4: Bargaining; Group 5: Conflict Management.

Bargaining was a theme included following Pruitt & Rubin (1975, p.2), who consider both terms equivalent, while others refer to

bargaining as a negotiation of money and Negotiation on more complex social units. In this research, we adopted both terms as equivalents.

Figure 1, finally, illustrates the Research Design:

Bibliometric Analysis

Trend Analysis

Figure 2. Publications per Periods

Figure 2 shows a yearly number of publications in business and administration covering the subject's "Negotiation" and "Conflict Management" between 1900 and 2023. Observe the ever-increasing number of publications since the 1980s to date. The difference may be attributed to the offspring of the world wide web

that allowed information to be linked and accessible to everyone.

Figure 3. Publications per Periods per Themes

Figure 2 shows the findings of the iterative first round. Then, content, trend, citation, and network text analysis were performed, which emerging themes distribution are illustrated in Figure 3.

Table 4 illustrates the trend analysis per citations and themes, from 1900 to 2023, organized into periods.

Table 4. Citations per Theme (1900-2023)

Timeline	Negotiation	Business Negotiation	International Negotiation	Bargaining	Conflict Mgmt	Total
1900-1949	1.066	7.893	7.737	910		17.606
1950-1969	52.277	33.007	20.156	24.337	1.672	131.449
1970-1979	68.881	112.544	26.514	18.869	6.855	233.663
1980-1989	283.949	221.532	187.069	63.041	8.515	764.106
1990-1999	490.436	686.350	591.100	67.812	53.675	1.889.373
2000-2009	568.940	967.783	609.878	42.335	75.385	2.264.321
2010-2023	340.197	735.563	506.520	31.786	113.314	1.727.380
Total	1.805.746	2.764.672	1.948.974	249.090	259.416	7.027.898

Next, we gathered Publications' affiliations from the .csv file saved from Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007). Using <https://www.google.com/intl/pt-BR/maps/about/mymaps/> (Google My Maps), the geographical distribution of the leading publishers is illustrated in Figure 4.

Author Influence

The most cited contributions to the field of Negotiation and Conflict Management are introduced in Table 5.

Figure 4. Geographical Location of Publications

Table 5. Top 10 Citations

Rank	Citations	Author(s)	Year
1	46.320	J Von Neumann, O Morgenstern	2007
2	29.990	KN Waltz	2010
3	30.217	SR Arnstein	1969
4	26.487	JS Brown, A. Collins, P Duguid	1989
5	22.765	TC Schelling	1980
6	21.671	JE Stiglitz	2017
7	21.240	RL Keeney, H Raiffa	1993
8	19.393	RE Miles, CC Snow, AD Meyer	1978
9	15.961	FR Dwyer, PH Shurr, S Oh	1987
10	15.200	R Fisher, WL Ury, B Patton	2011

Network Text Analysis

A network map of keywords, titles, and abstracts was used to identify thematic clusters based on the assumption that keywords clustered together may indicate related topics. Figure 5 depicts the network text analysis utilizing algorithms for density-based spacing clustering and normalization. Using www.infrandus.com, we visualized the text-based data as a network graph, exposing insights and patterns based on the network properties, most of which involved "Negotiation."

Each color represents a cluster. In order to determine the current themes and evolving trends in the field, each cluster's research papers were thoroughly examined.

Figure 5. Network Analysis
Source: InfraNodus

Content Analysis

"Negotiation" has been identified as the core category of this work (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). The concept denotes a social interaction between parties that seek something from someone. In this sense, "Bargaining" is an equivalent, although some authors refer as to financial transaction. "Negotiation" consists of three subprocesses: "Business Negotiation," "International Negotiation," and "Bargaining."

"Business Negotiation" received 2,764,762 citations during the period, whereas "Negotiation" has been cited 1,805,746, and "International Negotiation" has been cited 1,948,974 times.

"Conflict Management," in turn, has been identified as the secondary category of this study. The concept denotes the perception of differences and strategies to manage divergencies in the search for a mutual deal. Conversely, "Conflict Management" has been cited 259,416 times, similar to "Bargaining, cited 249,090 times.

Discussion

The current study aims to shed more light on the Negotiation and Conflict Management literature by providing an overview of the most frequently cited themes. Curiously, the findings pointed out a different direction than expected regarding the subjects investigated. Some surprises were revealed with the evidence, such as “Business Negotiations” being cited more than the field of Research “Negotiation.” We expected the inverse, as if business negotiations were part of a larger domain. Regarding “Bargaining,” we expected higher citations due to the similarities with “Negotiation.” Regarding “Conflict Management,” the findings surprised the authors, who considered a much higher bibliometric performance.

In addition, the systematic review extracted pertinent information from the existing literature. With the evidence gathered in the current study in mind, we share some observations and discuss implications for future research. Firstly, the answers to the research questions RQ1, RQ2, RQ3, and RQ4 are introduced.

RQ1: How did Negotiation and Conflict Management evolve throughout the last 120 years?

The answer to RQ1 is shown in Table 4. Over the past century, Negotiation has been investigated roughly seven times more than Conflict Management (1,805,746 vs. 259,416 citations). Moreover, Figures 2 and 3 illustrate an ever-increasing number of publications and citations. Note that the World Wide Web in the 1990s promoted knowledge dissemination like never before in human history.

RQ2: What is the most prominent and cited topic of both?

The answer to RQ2 is depicted in Table 3 and Figure 6. Evidence suggests four themes supporting scattered findings since some authors publish more than one topic per article (some literature reviews, for instance). The exhaustive process, however, is far from being definitive and error-free. Therefore, “Business Negotiation” was the most prominent theme

cited, performing 2,764,672 citations, as illustrated in Figure 6:

Figure 6. Citation Distribution

RQ3: What are the leading authors in the fields?

Table 5 reveals the top ten publications and leading authors in the fields, highlighting Jon von Neuman’s and Morgenstern’s “Theory of games and economic behavior,” and Arnstein’s “A ladder of citizen participation.” Fisher, Ury, and Patton’s “Getting to Yes: Negotiating agreement without giving in” completes the top ten most prominent authors in the fields’ list.

RQ4: What is the geographical spread of citations?

Figure 4 depicts the answer to question RQ4. In addition to North America and Europe, the distribution extends to other continents. Numerous citations indicate that the United States is the foremost nation.

However, only English-language articles were investigated. Consequently, additional research is required to investigate the global impact of other languages on Negotiation and Conflict Management.

Implications and Research limitations

This research aimed at mapping Negotiation and Conflict Management, understanding the most cited works throughout the last 123 years. However, the scope of this research is restricted to the subjects mentioned. Other topics, such as Buyer-seller, Government, Environmental and

ethics in Negotiations, are beyond the scope of the current study and need to be looked into independently. This research has implications and ramifications for many areas of study, including for instance: (i) business negotiations (Dias et al., 2022; Dias, 2020; Dias et al., 2022; Cunha & Dias, 2021; Dias, 2020b); (ii) teleworking (Schimtz & Dias, 2023); (iii) banking (Dias et al., 2022); (iv) Remote leadership (Dias, Pereira, Vieira, and Pan, 2022); (v) information security and leadership (Vieira & Dias, 2022); (vi) virtual teaching (Dias and Lopes, 2020; Dias et al., 2020); (vii) retail business (Dias & Falconi, 2018). This work ultimately benefits academics, leaders, decision-makers, policymakers, and other practitioners.

Conclusion and Future Research

The themes from the literature review are based on meticulously considering previous conceptualizations, arguments, and theories presented by previous researchers in the field, along with citations.

Through systematic literature evaluations, it is possible to reduce the uncertainty that has involved Negotiation studies for more than a century, thereby paving the way for future research. In addition, examination and practice will be enhanced as practitioners and analysts share their perspectives on these intricate topics. In addition, this article will advance research into frequently overlooked areas and strengthen the theoretical basis for future interventions and estimates. We conclude that Negotiation has gained prominence over the past four decades and that academicians have made contributions to the discipline worldwide. In addition, future research in other research disciplines, such as other languages and databases, is encouraged.

Conflict of Interests

No potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

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